

Design and testing of systolic array multiplier using fault injecting schemes

Kurada Verra Bhoga Vasantha Rayudu¹, Dhananjay Ramachandra Jahagirdar¹, Patri Srihari Rao²

¹Scientist'G'Head, Reliability Engineering Division, Research Centre Imarat, Kurmalguda, India

²Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, NIT Warangal, Hanamkonda, India

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays low power design circuits are major important for data transmission and processing the information among various system designs. One of the major multipliers used for synchronizing the data transmission is the systolic array multiplier, low power designs are mostly used for increasing the performance and reducing the hardware complexity. Among all the mathematical operations, multiplier plays a major role where it processes more information and with the high complexity of circuit in the existing irreversible design. We develop a systolic array multiplier using reversible gates for low power appliances, faults and coverage of the reversible logic are calculated in this paper. To improvise more, we introduced a reversible logic gate and tested the reversible systolic array multiplier using the fault injection method of built-in self-test block observer (BILBO) in which all corner cases are covered which shows 97% coverage compared with existing designs. Finally, Xilinx ISE 14.7 was used for synthesis and simulation results and compared parameters with existing designs which prove more efficiency.

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Corresponding Author:

Kurada Verra Bhoga Vasantha Rayudu

Scientist'G'Head, Reliability Engineering Division, Research Centre Imarat

Vignyanakancha Po, Hyderabad-500069, Kurmalguda, India

Email: kvbvr1@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Many multipliers are used to achieve low power and high-speed performance, In DSP systems, most of the DSP applications are designed for power dissipation and components used as multipliers [1]–[5] and to perform various high-speed operations multiplications play a major role in winding up the design. Mainly multiplication is an algorithm used at a structural level. Multi-dimension multiplication is done by the systolic array multipliers, those multipliers are a sequence of channels and it's a pipe lining process with a linear arrangement. When the multiplication process happens, it stores the information itself and processes it to the next pipeline level, and maintains a pipelining process, each block of the systolic array multiplier is fixed and looks similar. The simultaneous process performs in systolic arrays which increases the speed of the system and reduces the processing time with perfect efficiency of the output. Systolic array Multipliers are used for sorting and convolution techniques.

In this paper, we developed a systolic array design with the new model gate which decreases the delay and increases the speed of the operation, first of the multiplicand and multiplier are arranged in an array structure, and from the both of each bit is collected and do multiplicand, and its processes to the later pipeline stage, partial products, and carry generation done in the later stages. From the statement of the great scientist Landauer energy is dissipated at each bit of lost when transmits data with a particular amount of energy, the basic formula for calculating the loss of each bit of energy dissipated as $KT \cdot \log_2$, T defines

absolute temperature and K Defines Boltzmann's Constant. Reversible logic proved that we can minimize the dissipation of the heat by Charles Bennet [6], [7]. Reversible design is the future for developing circuits for low power and high-speed operations with very few system designs used. The main structures of the reversible gates are designed in such a way that the number of inputs is equal to the number of outputs. By this, it improves the overall performance of the systems [8]–[10]. In this paper systolic array multiplier is designed using reversible technology; it means all the components of the design use reversible gates to achieve the low power targets. Most of the system designs are being developed by reversible gates but testing was more complex and to reach the time to market it depends on the way of testing.

In the existing paper [11], [12] developed the systolic array multiplier with reversible gates, and proposed a multiplier for 4x4 systolic array design which calculates partial products and passes the partial products for carrying select generation, the testing to be done but simulated the design using the design tools and verified only parts of the design through simulations. In this paper [13], [14] they have proposed a new level of testing using BILBO logic where we can find the number of faults, but they have tested for Baugh Wooley multiplier designs. Most of the Baugh Wooley designs are used for high-speed operations, and also when we change the increased number of the bits for operations, we required more logic for the testing and implementation. The researchers [15], [16] addressed fault analysis techniques for computing multipliers by reviewing different methodologies of converting matrix algorithms to a predefined systolic array designs and then introduces array structure of the systolic part designs which was originally designed by the Lang and Moreno. Morghade *et al.* [17] Proved the design was correct by using the simulations and all the logic that implemented was algorithms for multiplication, division and direct multiplications methods, have examined various methods of testing they come up with LFSR technique which generates the random number of values for testing and applied and got succeeded and then moved for shift register designs which actually increases the area of the chip. The researchers [18]–[20] proposes a new method of approach for reducing the power consumption on an irreversible array multiplier and also using the reversible logic designs for the systolic array multiplier designs, which they expected to get high-end of the efficiency of the output in which compared with existing they end up with good results and also tested with 90ns CMOS nanometer technology. The researchers [21]–[24] which comes over a GF has made a bright application over the security of the multiplications and developed systolic array multiplier design over GF multiplier designs with full pattern generator using a six-bit counter and generate number of patterns required for the testing of the system designs for GF multiplier designs where it increases delay in the circuit and in the proposed system, we have overcome the issue of the delay removal of GF in the proposed system. The Proposed system of the research is to design an advanced systolic array multiplier with a new modified gate and test using fault injection method using BILBO logic for generating different patterns of test vectors.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Nowadays many low-power applications use reversible gate designs for low area and power. Because the logic present in reversible gates like no of input variables is equal to the number of output variables [25] where the utilization of power is used equally for fan outs, it is used for low power relevance designs. Quantum cost also reduces with the main logic involved in reversible designs. The majority plays an important role in reducing power dissipation due to the garbage and constant inputs used, when the circuit has garbage outputs power utilization is reduced due to which power loss is less. Reversible logic design selected for the project for low power dissipation and the reversible gate has been modified and is used for full adder design circuit, namely modified Islam gate shown in Figures 1 and 2. Modified Islam gate has 4 inputs and 4 outputs which output reflect as full adder model designs usage.

We have used controlled operational gate design which is used for getting full adder to carry select block, COG gate has now inputs and outs are equal i.e., 3, where logic completely depends on the second and third input variables, based on the status of that variables logic changes and works for full adder carrier output. Mostly COG reversible designs used for low power circuits in DSP Application for having the number of multiplier designs to get partial products intern to get resultant carry generation blocks, in our project we defined for the usage of carrier output.

Figure 1. Reversible modified Islam gate

Figure 2. Reversible controlled operational gate

By Integrating the above two reversible gates MIG and COG we get a complete adder and subtractor, which is used for systolic array multiplication, in systolic array multiplication it is used for multiplication, the process will be briefed in section 2.2. Mostly reversible full adder in Figure 3 plays a major role in any of the applications like video, medical, and many digital world systems

Figure 3. Reversible full adder /full subtractor

2.1. Systolic array multiplier cell block

Systolic array multiplier cell block is the special block for multiplication operation in which integration of sub designs like COG, MIG, and a complete formation of full adder block used for getting the resultant of the partial product of the design. For the function of the gate, the operation used the Toffoli gate which perfectly fits to reduce the power of the circuit. Multiplier cell block starts by taking individual bits of each of the Toffoli gate block as multiplicand and multiplier and generates the partial products with the usage of the reversible full adder design block. It is also a pipelining process in the systolic array multiplication model. Proposed full adder using reversible gates used for generating resultant and carry. Many of the instances of the block are used for reducing the coding of the design and re-use method performed, when one gets inputs other will be in the processing stage, and the Same way the process continues whole instances gets inputs and generate sums and carries. We are using a 4-bit multiplication process in which 16 multiplier cells are used for getting the full results of the systolic array multiplier. All the operations will be in the pipeline process and scheduled with each block to perform to get the value of the assigned bit and send to the other block and vice versa. Need to be very careful at the time of integrating the output of one block carry to the other multipliers cell block as shown in Figure 4, it may mislead the design for the wrong operation, it should be according to Endian format righted to left addition or connecting of the designs to the previous block of the carry bit.

Figure 4. Multiplier cell block

2.2. System design & testing method

Proposed system systolic array multiplier design and testing are to verify the multiplier corner cases as it is very complexing in finding the faults and compare the faults with existing system designs and improvement over the area, speed, power and find the faults. The proposed system mainly consists of four main blocks DUT, GRM, BILBO, and a checker as shown in Figure 5. Design under test which is proposed systolic array design, where mainly multiplication process goes on, Systolic Array multiplier developed using reversible gates and compared to the existing design we have proposed a new gate which performs faster than existing systolic array multiplier design. Multiple data bits are used for multiplication purposes. Mainly in systolic array multiplier design consists of 4 stages, whereas in 3 stages carry generated by the multiplier cell blocks were moved to the other stage multiplier cellblock design, whereas in stage 4 side by side the carrier moves to generate the final results of the multiplier block. Golden reference models are used for many of the

testing and verification SOC designs, GRM the coding part can be user-defined and it can be of any language, but it should work exactly as DUT, In this project reference model is taken as VHDL model for easy understanding of the flow of the multiplier at each stage of the block, when BIBLO generates the patterns, GRM also picks up the values and used for generating the outputs, the main focus is to get injected with the sum of the faults into the reference design, with the BILBO logic to get compared with the signature values to get the exact faults where has injected.

Figure 5. The proposed system with DUT and all required components

DUT Circuit which is used for testing could be placed in middle of the BILBOs, which are mostly working in the relevant modes as Linear feedback shift register and MISR modes. To test the circuit of SAM, a 4-bit multiplier design and an 8-bit BILBO were used. YAG gate design [26] is used for generating sum and product terms simultaneously. Input signal always in SCAN Mode If the BILBO uses LFSR mode, it generates the no of patterns required for the multiplier and the multiplier takes the inputs and intakes the output to the BILBO, which performs the operations to generate the signature like MISR Mode. If there is a signature produced for no-fault injection circuits called a good signature. Now the process begins will inject the faults in the design and generate the LFSR mode and gets patterns and generates the signature and that signature compares with the existing signature. If both matches, it proves testing did not happen correctly or fault is not identified by BILBO, if not BILBO detected fault. Checkers are most common in verification areas; checkers are named as scoreboard logics in which the two different data received from two blocks are to be compared and verified whether matched or mismatched to get the resultant of usage of DUT. Checkers are coded in the environment and tested the SAM circuit by injecting faults and by not injecting faults. In this project, a comparison is done between GRM and DUT outputs and storing the resultant for future usage.

As the process starts BILBO starts generating the patterns using modes, those patterns carried out within the environment and given to reversible systolic array multiplier, it processes the number of patterns it receives as it works as a pipeline stage multiplier, it generates the resultant and gives to the checker logic whereas simultaneous process happens in reference model used and also BILBO starts generating patterns at the same time, from the environment we are injecting the faults, one time stuck at 0/1 fault injected, and we see resultant is wrong than expected as in the Same BILBO logic gives a significant value as false, then the design will be corrected if BILBO passes as good signature it is failed to verify the design, hence the design should be modified depends on logic preferred.

Hence, the process of testing continues with various injections of faults, and results are compared using a checker. According to the research, many BIST architectures had been proposed but BILBO has played a vital role in the present generation as in SAM Project, we can configure it as an input generation of patterns in a full environment as shown in Figure 6, and also can be configured as output analyzer. Depending on the selection of inputs like b1 and b2, the mode can be selected. Various fault models discussed in [27]–[29] Compare to all techniques BIST technique is more popular because of its low power and less time of execution, complex designs also get testing done very fast, BILBO called LOGIC BIST because of using BIST as the main component in it and used for operating modes. Mainly in this project, a reversible multiplier is used for testing using the reversible BILBO logic applied for finding two main faults SAF, MSAF, and MGF faults of the design. Stuck at faults are rare faults that occur in designs and can be more complexes to find the faults whether to zero or one, Multiple stuck at faults also a rare finding of faults in conventional designs and Missing gate fault changes the output of the design, finding these types of faults are the most important nowadays to make fault free system designs [30], [31].

Figure 6. Full environment and testing with proposed systolic array multiplier using fault injection schemes

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows the systolic array multiplier resultant using the new modified Islam gate and the resultant can be calculated from the below fig as $1111 * 1111 = 011100001$. From Figure 8 we can say that various patterns have been generated for the Sam circuit which gets resultant true as it is mentioned in decimal $14 * 15 = 210$. Internal blocks of the design gates output resultant are shown in Figure 9.

In Figure 10, the concept of injection logic tried to inject the faults by missing some of the gates in the design which resulted in missing gate fault but here we can see the output does not break because of the reversible logic gates usage. Figure 11 shows the pattern generated from BILBO logic of LFSR mode, which generates random patterns as shown.

From Figure 12 and comparison values generated from the BILBO logic which proves stuck at fault findings at nearest value, as the design gets tested and compared with the existing signature after injecting faults.

Figure 7. Resultant of reversible systolic array multiplier using pattern generator from BILBO logic design

Figure 8. Resultant systolic array multiplier

Figure 9. Resultant of SAM internal blocks COG and MIG gates

Figure 10. Resultant of missing gate fault

Figure 11. Resultant of BILBO LFSR mode

Figure 12. Resultant of BILBO MISR mode signature comparison

Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is FAILED----The output is correct at required places
 $x_1=1, x_2=0, x_3=0, x_4=1, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=1, \text{out}=1, 3100$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is PASSED
 $x_1=0, x_2=0, x_3=1, x_4=0, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=0, \text{out}=0, 3200$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is FAILED----The output is correct at required places
 $x_1=1, x_2=0, x_3=0, x_4=0, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=0, \text{out}=0, 3300$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is FAILED----The output is correct at required places
 $x_1=0, x_2=1, x_3=1, x_4=0, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=0, \text{out}=1, 3400$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is PASSED
 $x_1=1, x_2=0, x_3=0, x_4=1, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=1, \text{out}=0, 3500$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is FAILED----The output is correct at required places
 $x_1=0, x_2=0, x_3=1, x_4=0, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=0, \text{out}=1, 3600$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is PASSED
 $x_1=1, x_2=0, x_3=0, x_4=0, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=0, \text{out}=0, 3700$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is FAILED----The output is correct at required places
 $x_1=0, x_2=1, x_3=1, x_4=0, x_5=0, \text{scan_in}=0, \text{out}=0, 3800$
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is FAILED----The output is correct at required places

x1=1, x2=0, x3=0, x4=1, x5=0, scan_in=1, out=1, 3900
 Finding test vector of the resultant at stuck at 0/1 is PASSED
 x1=0, x2=0, x3=1, x4=0, x5=0, scan_in=0, out=0, 4000

Table 1 and Table 2 have been shown a comparison of different multipliers for fault analysis of conventional and proposed design and also fault analysis at stuck-at faults, table values are collected using synthesis process of Xilinx ISE, where we have used vertex family for FPGA designs and improved the execution time unit.

Table 1. Comparison of multipliers from BILBO logic

Fault analysis	Conventional multiplier [10]	Proposed multiplier
Good signature	200	200
No of faults	138	138
No of faults detected	130	134
Fault coverage	96%	97%

Table 2. Comparison of multipliers after synthesizing the design using XILINX ISE 14.7

Local utilization	Conventional multiplier [10]	Proposed multiplier
No of slices	76.11%	70.2%
No of 4 input LUTs	26%	25%
Time delays	28.24%	28%
Area covered	75%	68%

4. CONCLUSION

Compared to the existing system designs, we proved that the design of the modified gate of systolic array multiplier design works faster because of reversible gate which has equal no of inputs and outputs which process the information faster and used for many low power high-speed applications. There is much scope to optimize the designs using the new reversible gates implementation. The proposed MIG gate reduces the gate count by 10% compared to the conventional designs and all other parameters to optimization mark. Most efficient testing was also done for SAM circuit to find the convenient faults as SAF and MGF preferably, we achieved coverage of patterns generation tested as 100%. Moreover, BILBO logic is implemented and is used for finding various faults for various system designs. Fault coverage using BILBO logic achieved 97% higher than the convention system designs. Future designs of SOC or subsystems can integrate and use for the detection of fault blocks of the design.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Kurada Verra Bhoga Vasantha Rayudu graduated from Institution of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineers (IETE), New Delhi during Dec 1990 and obtained MS (Electronics & Control) from BITS, Pilani. Served as Scientist up to 2002 at ISRO Satellite Centre and currently as Scientist at Research Centre Imarat (RCI), DRDO, Hyderabad in R&QA activities of MRSAM, LRSAM, PDV Mk-02 (Mission Shakti ASAT) Missile and Weapon Systems and related Avionic Systems. Contributed significantly in Parts Management, Qualification, Testing, Failure Analysis, reliability Analysis & Screening Policy of Electronic Components & Systems for Aerospace Applications. Planned and Played Key role for ISO 9001:2015 Certification and Aerospace Quality Management System AS 9100:2016 certification to RCI, Hyderabad. His Research Interests include VLSI Testing, VLSI Fault Simulation, Modeling & Diagnosis, Reliability Analysis, Failure Analysis, Quality Management System Certifications, applications of ANN, GA, SVM for optimization etc. Received Lal C Verman Award (2015) from IETE, New Delhi for significant contributions in Quality & Reliability assurance of Missile Systems. He can be contacted at email: kvbvr1@gmail.com

Dhananjay Ramachandra Jahagirdar received his B.E. degree in Electronics Engineering in 1990, from Govt. College of Engineering, Amravati University, Maharashtra, India. He received M. Tech. in Microwave Engineering in 1992, from Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, West Bengal, India. He was a Research Assistant at Sponsored Research and Industrial Consultancy at IIT, Kharagpur. Later, he joined Antenna Products Division of Electronics Corporation of India Ltd, Hyderabad. He obtained Ph. D. in 1997 from the Department of Electronics and Computer Science, University of Southampton, UK. He received scholarship from the Commonwealth Scholarship Commission UK to pursue PhD. He joined Research Centre Imarat, DRDO, Hyderabad in May 2000. He has won 'Best Paper Award' at the University of Leeds, UK organized by IEEE UKRI section. He has received Prof. S.K. Mitra memorial award for 'Best research-oriented paper' from IETE in 2002. He received young scientist award at IETE-IRSI International Radar symposium Bangalore in 2005. He also received laboratory scientist of the year award for 2006. He is a Fellow of IETE and senior member of IEEE, Antennas and Propagation Society and Microwave Theory and Techniques Society. He is also a member of URSI. Recently he has been listed in Marquis' Who's who in the world. His area of interest is microwave antennas and arrays for radars. He can be contacted at email: DR.Jahagirdar@rcilab.in

Patri Srihari Rao is working as Assoc Prof at NIT Warangal in the dept. of ECE. His Research interests include RFIC Design, VLSI Testing, Fault Diagnosis Analog/digital IC design, VLSI Testing Fault Diagnosis Analog/Digital IC Design, DSP Architecture, Analog LDO's. He has published numerous technical papers in Reputed international journals/Presented in Conferences. He has conducted various training courses and Workshops/Seminars at National/Internal Level and guided many PhD students. He can be contacted at email: patri@nitw.ac.in